

SHAYBONIYLAR DAVLATI VA USMONLI TURKLAR DAVLATI O'RTASIDAGI DASTLABKI ALOQALAR TAVSIFI

Xayrullayev Umidjon Fayzullo o'g'li

Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyozovich

Rahmonova Sanoat Shuhrat qizi

Osiyo Xalqaro universiteti "Ijtimoiy fanlar va texnika fakulteti

Tarix va filologiya kafedrası o'qituvchilari.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14613526>

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada O'zbek davlatchilik tarixida muayyan o'rniga ega bo'lgan Shayboniylar davlati va Usmonli turklar sultonligi o'rtasida qisman yo'lga qo'yilgan diplomatik va elchilik aloqalari haqida so'z boradi. Ikki davlatning aloqalari asosan Eron safaviylarga qarshi umumiy dushman sifatida qarash va Shialarga qarshi Sunniylarni qo'llab-quvvatlash negizida amalga oshiriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Chaldiran, sulton Salim I yovuz, yanichar, Astraxan, sunniy, shia, Safaviylar, Shayboniylar, Navro'z Ahmadxon, sulton Salim II, Ko'chkunchixon, Shayboniyxon.

DESCRIPTION OF THE EARLY RELATIONS BETWEEN THE SHAYBANI STATE AND THE OTTOMAN TURKS

Abstract. This article discusses the partially established diplomatic and embassy relations between the Shaybani state, which had a certain place in the history of Uzbek statehood, and the Ottoman Sultanate. The relations of the two states were mainly based on the perception of Iran as a common enemy against the Safavids and the support of the Sunnis against the Shiites.

Keywords: Chaldiran, Sultan Salim I evil, janissary, Astrakhan, Sunni, Shia, Safavids, Shaybanis, Navruz Ahmadkhan, Sultan Salim II, Kochkunchikhan, Shaybanikhan.

ОПИСАНИЕ РАННИХ ОТНОШЕНИЙ МЕЖДУ ГОСУДАРСТВОМ ШАЙБАНИ И ГОСУДАРСТВОМ ОСМАНСКИХ ТУРКОВ

Аннотация. В данной статье говорится о частично установившихся дипломатических и посольских отношениях между государством Шайбани, занимающим особое место в истории узбекской государственности, и Султанатом турок-османов. Отношения между двумя странами в основном основаны на восприятии Ирана как общего врага против Сефевидов и поддержке суннитов против шиитов.

Ключевые слова: Чалдыран, Султан Салим I Злой, Яничар, Астрахань, Сунниты, Шииты, Сефевиды, Шайбани, Навруз Ахмад-хан, Султан Салим II, Кочкунчи-хан, Шайбани-хан.

Shayboniylar sulolasining (1500–1601) Turkiya (Usmonli imperiyasi) bilan bo'lgan aloqalari XV asr oxiri va XVI asr boshlariga to'g'ri keladi. Ushbu aloqalar, asosan, ikki davlatning mintaqaviy geosiyosiy manfaatlariga bog'liq bo'lib, davriy diplomatik va harbiy munosabatlarda ifodalangan.

Shayboniylar sulolasi va Usmonli turklar o'rtasidagi dastlabki aloqalarni uch davrga bo'lish mumkin:

1) Usmonli-Shayboniylar munosabatlari (1500-1510 yillar):

Shayboniylar sulolasi O'rta Osiyoda Movarounnahr hududida hukmronlikni qo'lga kiritgan davrda, Usmonli imperiyasi Yaqin Sharqda kuchaygan payt edi. Shayboniylar va Usmonlilar o'rtasidagi dastlabki diplomatik aloqalar aniq bo'lmasa-da, ikki tomon bir-birini kuzatgan. Shayboniixon (Muhammad Shayboniixon) 1500-yillarning boshida Eron safaviylariga qarshi kurash olib borgan va bu kurashda Usmonli imperiyasining ham manfaatlar mavjud edi¹. Usmonlilar Eron Safaviylari bilan raqobatda bo'lgan va Shayboniylarning Safaviylarga qarshi faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashni o'ylagan. Ammo bu davrda Shayboniylar va Usmonli imperiyasi o'rtasida muhim bir kelishuv yoki ittifoq shakllanmagan.

2) 1510-yilda Shayboniixonning o'limi:

1510-yilda Shayboniixon Safaviylar hukmdori Shoh Ismoil bilan bo'lgan Marv yaqinidagi jangida halok bo'ldi. Bu voqea Usmonli imperiyasi va Shayboniylar o'rtasidagi ehtimoliy aloqalarga ham ta'sir qildi, chunki Usmonli imperiyasi Safaviylarning kuchayishidan xavotirda edi va bu voqea Eron va Usmonli munosabatlariga ham ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

3) 1530-1560-yillar: Shayboniylar va Usmonli munosabatlari:

Shayboniylar sulolasining keyingi hukmdorlari davrida (masalan, Ubaydullaxon va Abdulatifxon) Usmonli imperiyasi bilan bevosita harbiy ittifoq tuzilmagan bo'lsa-da, diplomatik aloqalar mavjud bo'lgan. Bu davrda Usmonli imperiyasi Yevropa va Eron bilan ko'proq shug'ullangan bo'lsa, Shayboniylar O'rta Osiyodagi o'zaro ichki va tashqi kurashlar bilan band edi. Biroq, ikkala davlat ham Safaviylar Eroniga qarshi umumiy manfaatlariga ega edi.

Umuman olganda, Shayboniylar sulolasi va Usmonli imperiyasi o'rtasidagi aloqalar cheklangan va asosan mintaqaviy geosiyosiy o'zgarishlarga bog'liq bo'lgan. Sulola davrida Usmonli-Shayboniylar munosabatlari muhim darajada rivojlanmagan bo'lsa-da, Safaviylar bilan bo'lgan dushmanlik umumiy manfaatlariga asoslangan, ammo kuchli ittifoq shakllanmagan. 1514-yilda Usmonli imperatori Sulton Salim I va Safaviy Shoh Ismoil o'rtasidagi Chaldiran jangida Usmonlilar g'alaba qozonadi².

¹ M.Qodirov -Shayboniylar tarixi: Siyosiy va madaniy aloqalar.T-2020 58 b.

² P.M.Holt, K.S Lambton, B.Lewis "The Central Islamic Lands from Pre-Islamic Times to the First World War" Volume 1A Cambridge University Press, 2008y, p-400

Bu jangda Shayboniylar bevosita ishtirok etmagan, ammo Safaviylarga qarshi kurash Usmonlilar va Shayboniylarning umumiy manfaatiga mos keladi. Shayboniylar uchun bu voqea Safaviylarning kuchayishiga qarshi kurashni davom ettirishga imkon yaratadi. Ko'chunchixon davrida 1515-yil Sulton Salim I huzuriga Shayboniylar elchisi tashrif buyuradi kata ehtimol bilan bu elchilikning maqsadi Eron Safaviylarga qarshi ittifoqni tashkil qilish va yaxshi hamkorlik aloqalarni yo'lga qo'yish bo'lgan³. Bundan tashqari Shayboniylar sulolasining vakili Navro'z Ahmadxon (Baroqxon) ning Toshkentdagi saroyida 300 nafar turk yanichari uning xizmatida bo'lgan. Yanicharlarni Usmonlilar hukmdori Sulton Salim I 1554-yil sunniylarni qo'llab quvvatlash maqsadida ya'ni Safaviylarga qarshi kurashda foydalanishi uchun Navro'z Ahmadxon huzuriga jo'natgan⁴.

Lekin Navro'z Ahmadxon bu yanicharlardan taxt uchun kurashlarda foydalanganligi haqida ma'lumotlar mavjud. O'rta Osiyolik musulmonlar bu davrda Haj ziyorati uchun Makkaga Astaraxan orqali borishardi chunki asosiy yo'l Eron orqali o'tardi va uni Safaviylar nazorat qilar edi. Sulton Salim II davrida Samarqand, Buxoro va ayniqsa, Xorazm xonlari sultonga maktub yo'llab, Eron shohi va Rossiya Astraxanda ziyoratchilar va savdogarlarni to'xtatayotganidan shikoyat qiladilar. Ular Usmonlilardan Astraxanni egallashni so'rashdi, shunda hech bo'lmaganda o'sha shahar orqali ziyorat yo'li ochiladi⁵. Shayboniylar sulolasi va Usmonli imperiyasi o'rtasidagi aloqalar, asosan, geosiyosiy manfaatlarga asoslangan va Eron Safaviylariga qarshi umumiy dushmanlik bilan belgilanadi. Shayboniylar asosan O'rta Osiyo va Eronning ichki masalalari bilan shug'ullangan, Usmonli imperiyasi esa Yaqin Sharq va Yevropaga qaratilgan kengroq siyosat yuritgan.

REFERENCES

1. M.Qodirov -Shayboniylar tarixi: Siyosiy va madaniy aloqalar. T-2020
2. I.Karimov Markaziy Osiyo va Turkiya o'rtasidagi tarixiy aloqalar. Tashkent: Yoshlar -2018.
3. A.Saidov Turkiya va Shayboniylar sulolasi: Madaniy va iqtisodiy aloqalar. Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya-2017.
4. S.Tursunov O'zbekiston tarixi: Shayboniylar va Usmonli imperiyasi. Tashkent: Sharq – 2016.

³ I.Karimov Markaziy Osiyo va Turkiya o'rtasidagi tarixiy aloqalar. Tashkent: Yoshlar 2018y. 46b

⁴ P.M.Holt, K.S Lambton, B.Lewis "The Central Islamic Lands from Pre-Islamic Times to the First World War" Volume 1A Cambridge University Press, 2008y, p-333

⁵ P.M.Holt, K.S Lambton, B.Lewis "The Central Islamic Lands from Pre-Islamic Times to the First World War" Volume 1A Cambridge University Press, 2008y, p-333

5. P.M.Holt, K.S Lambton, B.Lewis "The Central Islamic Lands from Pre-Islamic Times to the First World War" Volume 1A Cambridge University Press, 2008
6. Xayrullayev, U. (2024). THE IDEA THAT MADE THE OTTOMAN STATE GREAT (RED APPLE II). *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1071–1073. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29533>
7. Xayrullayev, U. (2024). BRIEFLY ABOUT THE "RED APPLE" MYTHOLOGY OF THE TURKS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 568–572. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28329>
8. Umidjon, X. (2024). Literacy and Information Exchange in the Ancient East and West. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 179–183. Retrieved from <http://www.inovatus.es/index.php/ejine/article/view/2698>
9. Umidjon, X. (2023). 1918-1939-yillarda Polshaning ichki siyosatidagi o'zgarishlar. *Центр Научных Публикаций (buxdu.Uz)*, 42(42). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/10963
10. Umidjon Xayrullayev. (2024). THE POSITION OF CENTRAL ASIAN GOVERNORSHIPS DURING THE PERIOD OF THE TURKISH KHANATE AND THE ARAB INVASION. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13958464>
11. Xayrullayev Umidjon Fayzullo o'g'li. (2024). LEGITIMACY OF RULERSHIP IN THE STATE OF CENTRAL ASIA AND IRAN IN ANCIENT TIMES AND THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14222295>
12. Xayrullayev, U. (2024). EFTALLAR DAVLATI VA TURK XOQONLIGIDA HUKMDORLIK LEGITIMATSIYASI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 843–851. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58469>
8. BIRINCHI RADIO EHTIYOTLAR TARIXIDAN. (2024). *MEDICINE, PEDAGOGY AND TECHNOLOGY: THEORY AND PRACTICE*, 2(4), 657-663. <https://universalpublishings.com/index.php/mpttp/article/view/5240>
13. Xayrullayev, U. (2024). TURK XOQONLIGI VA ARABLAR BOSQINI DAVRIDA O'RTA OSIYO HOKIMLIKLARINING MAVQEYI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 339–343. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/58055>
14. Xarullayev Umidjon. (2024). RELIGIOUS AND THREATS IN MEDIASPACE. МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА, 2(5), 593–595. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11311154>

15. Rahmonova Sanoat Shuhrat qizi. (2024). SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL REFORMS ARE THE FOUNDATION OF A NEW UZBEKISTAN. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14503228>
16. Rahmonova, S. (2023). DYNAMICS AND MAIN DIRECTIONS OF SPIRITUAL AND CULTURAL REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN UZBEKISTAN. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 850-854.
17. Rahmonova, S. (2023). YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA MA'NAVIY-MADANIY ISLOHOTLAR. *Current approaches and new research in modern sciences*, 2(10), 40-43.
18. Rahmonova, S. (2023). YUKSAK MA'NAVIYATLI AVLOD-UCHINCHI RENESSANS BUNYODKORLARI. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 2(3), 76-79.
19. Rahmonova, S. (2024). THE REFORMS IMPLEMENTED IN NEW UZBEKISTAN ARE THE FOUNDATION OF THE THIRD RENAISSANCE. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 394-399.
20. Qizi, R. S. S., Shukhratovna, T. S., & Karamatovna, M. A. (2024). Implementation of Education and Protection of Children's Rights in the age of Technology. *SPAST Reports*, 1(7).
21. Рахмонова, С. (2024). HARMONY OF EDUCATION AND TRAINING. *Журнал универсальных научных исследований*, 2(5), 366-375.
22. Ramatov, J., Hasanov, M., & Rahmonova, S. (2024). TA'LIM TIZIMI MODERNIZATSIYALASHUVINING IJTIMOY-FALSAFIY ASOSLARI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 4(8), 160-172.
23. Rahmonova, S. S. Q. (2024). O'ZBEKISTONDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN MA'NAVIY-MADANIY ISLOHOTLAR DINAMIKASI VA ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI. *International scientific journal of Biruni*, 3(2), 95-104.
24. Ilniyazovich, S. F. (2023). RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING TARIX FANINI O'QITISHDAGI AHAMIYATI.
25. Ilniyoz o'g'li, S. F. (2023). ETNOGRAFIK TADQIQOTLARDA QORAQALPOQ XALQINING YORITILISHI.
26. Ilniyazovich, S. F. (2024). The Formation of Preliminary Knowledge about the People of Karakalpak. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(3), 149-155.
27. Sayfutdinov, F. (2024). BUXORO AMIRLIGINING QURILISH TARIXI: MADANIY VA ARXITEKTURA TARAQQIYOTI MEROSI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 852-858.

28. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyoz o'g'li. (2023). XX ASR 2-YARMI XXI ASR BOSHLARI ZARAFSHON VOHASIDA ETNOSLARARO MUNOSABATLAR. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(9), 1–5. Retrieved from <https://sciencebox.uz/index.php/ajed/article/view/7941>
29. Sayfutdinov F. (2024). ILLUMINATION OF THE SPIRITUAL LIFE OF THE KARAKALPAK PEOPLE IN RESEARCH. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 2(5), 441–452. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/universal-scientific-research/article/view/34891>
30. Sayfutdinov F. (2024). MANG'IT AMIRLARI DAVRIDA BUXORO AMIRLIGI ME'MORCHILIK SOHASI RIVOJI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(10), 620–629. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/45335>
31. Ilniyazovich, S. F. (2024). Historiography of Various Expeditions and their Results in the Regions Inhabited by Karakalpaks in the First Half of the 20th Century. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4(9), 159-165.
32. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyoz o'g'li. (2023). XIX ASRDA XONLIKLARNING O'ZARO SAVDO MUNOSABATLARI. *JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING*, 2(8), 111–114. Retrieved from <http://jsrt.innovascience.uz/index.php/jsrt/article/view/284>
33. Sayfutdinov, F. (2023). ILLUMINATION OF KARAKALPAK PEOPLE IN ETHNOGRAPHIC STUDIES. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 910–917. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/27281>
34. Sayfutdinov, F. (2024). HISTORIOGRAPHY OF INFORMATION ABOUT THE POPULATION OF THE ZARAFSHAN OASIS. (20TH CENTURY). *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 911–914. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/29503>
35. Sayfutdinov F. (2024). ETHNIC COMPOSITION OF THE ZARAFSHAN OASIS (2ND HALF OF THE 20TH CENTURY). *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 577–581. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/28335>
36. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyozovich, . (2023). LAND OWNERSHIP RELATIONS BASED ON THE NATIONAL ECONOMY OF KARAKALPAK. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(11), 20–27. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue11-04>
37. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyozovich, . (2023). STUDY OF THE KARAKALPAK PEOPLE IN ETHNOLOGICAL SCIENTIFIC WORKS HISTORY . *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(12), 61–68. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue12-11>

38. Sayfutdinov, F. (2023). ANALYSIS OF DATA ON LAND OWNERSHIP AND LIVESTOCK FARMING OF KARAKALPAKS. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 650–657. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/25727>
39. Sayfutdinov Feruz Ilniyazovich, (2023). USING GIS SOFTWARE AND THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL HISTORY IN THE STUDY OF HISTORY. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(10), 31–33. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijhps/Volume03Issue10-06>
40. Sayfutdinov, F. (2023). THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN TEACHING HISTORY. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 719–723. Retrieved from <https://inlibrary.uz/index.php/science-research/article/view/24678>
41. Ilniyoz o'g'li, S. F. (2023). XIX ASRDA XONLIKLARNING O 'ZARO SAVDO MUNOSABATLARI. *JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING*, 2 (8), 111–114.
42. Toshpo'latova, S., Gadayeva, M., & Sadullayev, U. (2024). SHARQ ALLOMALARINING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 985-993.
43. Toshpo'latova Shaxnoza Shuhratovna. (2024). ILK UYG'ONISH DAVRI NAMOYONDALARINING DIDAKTIK QARASHLARI ASOSIDA O'QUVCHILARNI TARIX FANIGA QIZIQTIRIS METODIKASI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14520996>
44. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). TARIX FANINI O'QITISHDA SAMARALI METODLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(11), 774-782.
45. Тошполатова, Ш. (2024). THE PRESENT IRANIANS. *Журнал универсальных научных исследований*, 2(5), 453-462.
46. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). BUXORODAGI SAROYLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(5), 522-529.
47. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). O'RTA ASRLARDA OILA PEDAGOGIKASIGA OID FIKRLAR. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 353-361.
48. Toshpo'latova, S., & Xudoyqulov, S. (2024). History And Ethnology Of Olot District. *Modern Science And Research*, 3(5), 148-151.
49. Toshpo'latova, S., & Jo'rayeva, M. (2024). HISTORY AND ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF JONDOR DISTRICT. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 447-450.
50. Qizi, R. S. S., Shukhratovna, T. S., & Karamatovna, M. A. (2024). Implementation of Education and Protection of Children's Rights in the age of Technology. *SPAST Reports*, 1(7).
51. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2024). Linguistic Anthropology. *European Journal Of Innovation In Nonformal Education*, 4(3), 432-437.

52. Toshpo'latova, S. S., & Naimov, I. N. (2023). MS ANDREYEV-O'RTA OSIYO XALQLARI ETNOGRAFIYASINING YIRIK OLIMI. *Innovations in Technology and Science Education*, 2(8), 1214-1222.
53. Toshpo'latova, S., & Tursuntoshova, S. (2024). Khoja Abdulkholiq Gijduvani. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 87-93.
54. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). Ethnolinguistics Of Ethnologies Of Bukhara. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 1004-1011.
55. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). Ethnolinguistics. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(2), 500-507.
56. Toshpo'latova, S. (2024). Religious Anthropology. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(1), 504-510.
57. Shakhnoza Shuhratovna, T. (2023). MS Andreyev'S Way Of Life. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(10), 655-659.
58. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2023). Ethnological Analysis Of National Costumes And Rituals Of Tajiks In The Works Of MS Andreyev. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(12), 42-47.
59. Toshpo'latova, S. (2023). MS Andreyev-Scientific Career. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(12), 801-807.
60. Shuhratovna, T. S. (2023). Etymology Of Tajik Marriage Ceremony. *International Journal Of History And Political Sciences*, 3(11), 17-23.